

Fractionated Stereotactic Radiotherapy for POEMS Syndrome: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT Background: POEMS syndrome is a rare neoplastic entity. It has population incidence of 0.3/100,000 and presents predominantly on the 5th or 6th decade of life. Its treatment is considered to be multidisciplinary. Case summary: We present the case of a 47-year-old male patient with POEMS syndrome who was initially managed with chemotherapy but was treated with stereotactic radiation therapy for spinal cord compression associated due to a plasma cell neoplasm at the T6-T7 vertebral body. Conclusion: Radiation therapy is the preferred treatment modality for one to three isolated bone lesions, with a marked improvement in neuropathy.

KEYWORDS Fractionated Stereotactic radiotherapy, POEMS Syndrome, spinal cord compression.

Introduction

POEMS syndrome is a rare neoplastic entity. Resulting from a plasma cell neoplasm, first described in 1980 by Barkwick et cols (1), who gave the POEMS acronym based on the signs and symptoms found on these patients: polyneuropathy, organomegaly, endocrinopathy, monoclonal protein and skin changes. Also known as Takatsuki or Crow-Fukase syndrome (2,3), it has a population incidence of 0.3/100,000 and presents predominantly on the 5th or 6th decade of life. There are other manifestations such as papilledema, liquid extravasation, osteosclerosis, thrombocytosis, erythrocytosis, lung function abnormality and Castleman disease (4). The diagnosis is based on obligatory criteria, along with major and minor criteria. The obligatory criteria are polyneuropathy and plasma cell neoplasm, there need to be at least 1 major criteria; either Castleman disease, osteosclerosis and VEGF elevation, also at least 1 minor criteria needs to be present which can be organomegaly, liquid extravasation,

endocrinopathy, skin changes, papilledema, thrombocytosis and/or polycitemia (5,6). The pathogenesis is not yet well known, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is the only cytokine that appears to have a strong association, but it may not be the only one (7). Treatment is multidisciplinary, ranging from systemic steroid therapy, chemotherapy, targeted therapy and radiation therapy.

Objective:

To present the case of a patient with POEMS syndrome and spinal cord compression treated with radiation therapy.

Clinical case:

47-year-old male patient, he began in 2013 with skin pigmentation changes and lower extremity oedema, after this, he begins to develop pain in the thoracic column region and ribcage pain at deep inspiration. He also presents with polyneuropathy, anorexia and 35 kg weight loss. 12 months later he continues with neuropathy, which is progressive and causes loss of deambulation, he received symptomatic treatment with partial improvement, six months posterior he develops cervical and axillary adenopathy. A biopsy is taken of these lesions with a pathology report compatible with Castleman disease, Vascular-Hyaline variety. Chemotherapy with CHOP-R (cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, prednisone, and Rituximab) is initiated on March 2014, with a complete response of the cervical and axillary adenopathies. However, during the chemotherapy cycles, the neuropathy progressed to hemiplegia along with the

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DOI: 10.5455/IJMRCR.poems-syndrome-fractionated-stereotactic-radiotherapy
First Received: April 09, 2018

Accepted: May 31, 2018

Manuscript Associate Editor: George Baytchev (BG)

Reviewers: Ivan Inkov (BG), Masoud Sadeghi (IR)

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loss of sphincter control. Electromyography was done which reported mixed neuropathy, spine MRI showed a lesion at the T6-T7 vertebral body, with an invasion of the spinal canal and right posterior costal arch. Biopsy of this lesion reported: Plasma cell neoplasm, with monoclonality of LAMBDA 70%, KAPPA 10-20%. The bone lesion was managed with fractionated stereotactic radiation therapy for treatment of spinal cord compression syndrome (Figure 1).

Figure 1: description: Treatment planning was done in BrainLAB Treatment planning 5.31, with conformal dynamic arc technique (Pencilbeam).

Treatment was given using Exatrac localisation system, and a Brainlab Novalis 6MV linear accelerator. A 40 Gy dose was given in 20 sessions of 2 Gy each, with two isocenters (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Description: The extensive lytic lesion in the vertebral body and rib was included in Planning Target Volumen (PTV) for the radiation treatment.

Treatment was finalised in June 2014.

Two months after the radiation treatment, the patient presented to the department without pain at lumbar region and ribcage, he could deambulate with the help of a walker, no loss of sensitivity and 4/5-muscle strength in the Daniels-Worthington scale. A new MRI reports a reduction in the tumoral volume of approximately 30%, with the spinal canal being free. After a four year follow-up, the patient continues with clinical improvement and walking.

Discussion

The POEMS syndrome is a paraneoplastic disorder associated with the presence of bone plasmacytoma, which can be in the spine as in this case. The most frequent neurological complications related to the vertebral site is spinal cord compression, clinically characterised by back pain, radicular pain, sensory, motor and sphincter alterations[6].

Despite the aggressive behaviour of plasmacytomas, clonal plasma cells show high sensitivity to radiotherapy with high response rates with this management[7].

Our patient was treated with fractionated stereotactic radiotherapy with a dose of 40 Gy in 20 sessions, with partial response according to RECIST (Response Evaluation Criteria In Solid Tumors). Radical radiotherapy is the treatment of choice in the case of solitary plasmacytoma with a minimum dose of 40 Gy and can be scaled to 45-50 Gy in tumours > 5 cm. [8]. With local relapse rates of 14%, and local control rates of 86% to 5 years respectively, according to Oszahin. [9].

Conclusion:

Radical radiotherapy as a single modality is the treatment of choice for solitary plasmacytoma because clonal plasma cells show marked radiosensitivity, reaching local control rates higher than 80%. The average radiation dose with an adequate response is 40 Gy in conventional fractionation, and for tumours larger than 5 centimetres can be scaled up to 50 Gy.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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